

Self-Assembled Fluorinated Nanoparticles as Sensitive and Biocompatible Theranostic Platforms for ^{19}F MRI

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Theranostics is a novel paradigm integrating therapy and diagnostics, thereby providing new prospects for overcoming the limitations of traditional treatments. In this context, perfluorocarbons (PFCs) are the most widely used tracers in preclinical fluorine-19 magnetic resonance (^{19}F MR), primarily for their high fluorine content. However, PFCs are extremely hydrophobic, and their solutions often display reduced biocompatibility, relative instability, and subpar ^{19}F MR relaxation times. This study aims to explore the potential of micellar ^{19}F MR imaging (MRI) tracers, synthesized by polymerization-induced self-assembly (PISA), as alternative theranostic agents for simultaneous imaging and release of the non-steroidal antiepileptic drug clofazimine. In vitro, under physiological conditions, these micelles demonstrate sustained drug release. In vivo, throughout the drug release process, they provide a highly specific and sensitive ^{19}F MRI signal. Even after extended exposure, these fluoropolymer tracers show biocompatibility, as confirmed by the histological analysis. Moreover, the characteristics of these polymers can be broadly adjusted by design to meet the wide range of criteria for preclinical and clinical settings. Therefore, micellar ^{19}F MRI tracers display physicochemical properties suitable for in vivo imaging, such as relaxation times and non-toxicity, and high performance as drug carriers, highlighting their potential as both diagnostic and therapeutic tools.

1. Introduction

Theranostics, a portmanteau of “therapy” and “diagnostics” is an emerging and promising approach at the intersection of imaging, chemistry, biology, and medicine. This approach involves developing platforms combining drug delivery systems with diagnostic capabilities. By precisely integrating these modalities into a single platform, theranostics has a high potential for improving patient outcomes through personalized medicine.^[1,2] Theranostic platforms are primarily developed based on nanoparticle (NP) design.^[3–5] This design aims at creating systems for acquiring real-time information on disease status while simultaneously enabling appropriate treatment adjustments and personalized interventions. Moreover, theranostics systems enhance drug delivery to specific tissues or cells, minimizing off-target effects and thus improving therapeutic efficacy.^[6,7]

In theranostics, selecting an appropriate imaging modality is also crucial for acquiring accurate and specific diagnostic information.^[1] Among the various imaging

modalities available, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) stands out as a powerful, non-invasive, high-resolution imaging

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technique without ionizing radiation.^[8] Conventional proton hydrogen MRI (¹H MRI) excels at capturing detailed anatomical information, but its specificity is hindered by background signals of water and lipids when imaging biological tissues. Overcoming this inherent limitation requires the administration of contrast agents^[9] or heteronuclear (X-nuclei) probes^[10–12] capable of enhancing the signal specificity of targeted tissues and cells.

Among the most promising X-nuclei probes are fluorinated compounds, which offer several advantages for ¹⁹F MR. Firstly, the presence of physiological fluorine in living organisms is negligible, enabling highly specific “hotspot” visualizations. Secondly, the ¹⁹F isotope also has favorable properties for MR, such as 100% natural abundance, spin $I = 1/2$, and 83% MR sensitivity relative to ¹H. Furthermore, fluorinated solutions can be effectively visualized by clinical instruments with only minor hardware adjustments to radiofrequency coils.^[13–15] However, fluorine-rich tracers must be synthesized carefully considering the balance between particle stability, solubility, and content of chemically equivalent fluorine atoms.^[16] Unstable substances may undergo decomposition or react oddly with biological components, leading to unpredictable behavior.^[17] Poorly soluble substances may aggregate or precipitate, potentially blocking blood vessels or damaging tissues.^[18,19] Multiple fluorine-containing functional groups may result in a multi-peak spectrum with signal dispersion and decreased MR sensitivity. Other key factors should also be considered, particularly non-toxicity and reasonably short T_1 and long T_2 relaxation times.

Meeting these criteria, perfluorocarbons (PFCs), most notably perfluoro-crown-ethers (PFCEs) and perfluoropolyethers (PFPEs) are widely used in preclinical ¹⁹F MR.^[20,21] Yet, despite their high fluorine content, they are extremely hydrophobic and thus poorly soluble. As a result, their solutions often display reduced biocompatibility, relative instability, and subpar ¹⁹F MR relaxation times.^[22,23] Nevertheless, a possible alternative is to expand the use of fluoropolymers as probes. Thanks to their countless possibilities of polymer chain modification, fluoropolymers unlock several advantages not only for biomedical applications but also for other purposes.^[24,25]

Polymeric NP tracers can be synthesized using various methods, including aqueous polymerization-induced self-assembly (PISA).^[26] This synthetic route involves controlled polymerization of block copolymers, wherein one block is hydrophilic and the other is hydrophobic. Consequently, self-assembly occurs within aqueous settings during the polymerization process. This straightforward procedure is an effective method for synthesizing micellar NPs,^[27,28] supporting the design and engineering of fluorinated NPs with properties, such as size and morphology, tailored to the desired application.

Considering the potential of fluoropolymers as highly biocompatible ¹⁹F MR probes with excellent imaging properties, this study aims at i) developing and characterizing amphiphilic drug-conjugated fluorinated polymers based on *N*-(2,2,2-trifluoromethyl)acrylamide (TFEAM) as a core-forming monomer prepared by aqueous PISA and ii) assessing the potential of these NPs for drug encapsulation and release using the antimicrobial agent clofazimine. For this purpose, we assessed the diagnostic capabilities of this system by employing ¹⁹F MR imaging and spectroscopy (MRI/MRS) modalities and evaluated the clearance process of the NPs in a living organism.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Nanoparticle Synthesis

Self-assembled ¹⁹F MRI nanotracers were synthesized using the polymerization-induced self-assembly (PISA) method, wherein copolymer synthesis and micelle self-assembly proceed in a single step. Copolymer NPs were synthesized in water by reversible addition-fragmentation transfer (RAFT) polymerization from the water-soluble polyethylene glycol macromolecular chain-transfer agent (PEG-CTA, 4 kDa). PEG-CTA was extended *in situ* by a poly(*N*-(2,2,2-trifluoromethyl)acrylamide (TFEAM) fluorinated core-forming block, yielding fluorinated NPs, as described in our previous report.^[29] To improve the magnetic relaxation of the fluorinated micellar core and thus increase its signal intensity, a minor part of *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)acrylamide (HEAM, 20 mol%) was added to the copolymerization mixture.^[30] The total polymerization degree of 400 was selected to achieve optimal stability of micelles. Micelles with shorter hydrophobic blocks would have higher critical micelle concentration, while longer hydrophobic blocks would lead to micelle destabilization and macroscopic precipitation. The final structure of the diblock copolymer was PEG₉₁-*b*-P(TFEAM₃₂₀-*stat*-HEAM₈₀) (Scheme 1), henceforth referred to as fluorinated micelles (FluoroMic). The hydrodynamic size of the NPs was 140 nm, as determined by dynamic light scattering (DLS).

2.2. FluoroMic Detectability and Clearance

After our proof-of-concept study^[29] of such NPs, we investigated their *in vivo* detectability and clearance by spectroscopic imaging (MRSI) and MRS analysis. In practical theranostics applications, the diagnostic component should remain detectable in the organism for at least the duration of drug release to effectively monitor a substance with a therapeutic effect. However, the presence of a carrier must not be excessively prolonged to avoid potential complications. For instance, PFCs used in ¹⁹F imaging, such as PFCEs, have undesirably too long biological half-lives, when administered systematically.^[31]

In preparation for our experiments, we conducted a series of preliminary *in vivo* investigations using different subcutaneous injection volumes of FluoroMic solutions ($c_{\text{pol}} = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$). Unsurprisingly, lower volumes (50 μL) were insufficient to efficiently visualize the carrier for the desired period. In turn, using a 200 μL injection volume excessively prolonged clearance, presumably due to nanoparticle retention at the administration site. This retention raised concerns regarding the complete elimination of the nanoparticles from an organism. Thus, we decided to use 100 μL to avoid any unnecessary risk when conducting experiments with the mice. Through direct subcutaneous administration of FluoroMic at this volume into the right flank, we were also able to consistently determine the optimal positioning of mice for measurement and for placing the on-site reference ($c = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$, $V = 100 \mu\text{L}$) below the body. ¹⁹F MR signal originates from $\approx 5.325 \times 10^{20}$ fluorine atoms which are present at the given concentration and administered volume. Furthermore, by spectrally resolved MRSI analysis we were able to choose the frequency range of interest and suppress the omnipresent isofluorane signal, originating from anesthesia. The injected FluoroMic

Scheme 1. Synthesis of fluorinated block copolymer.

depot was detected by ^{19}F MRSI with a strong signal at ≈ 30 -min post-injection (PI) (**Figure 1a**) and with a less intense signal from the same area, confirming its clearance process, at 5 days PI (**Figure 1b**).

As MRS is more sensitive than MRI, we were able to detect a spectroscopic signal of the injected substance for an extended period. Using this capability, we assessed the in vivo clearance process. To ensure a more robust ^{19}F MRS data quantitation over time, we incorporated sodium fluoride (NaF) ($c = 4.2 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$, $V = 100 \mu\text{L}$) as an external reference because NaF has a chemical shift of $\Delta\delta = 47 \text{ ppm}$ from FluoroMic (**Figure 2a**). By incorporating a reference substance with a consistent concentration and a different chemical shift from FluoroMic, we aimed to minimize systematic errors and establish a reliable baseline for comparison. Subsequently, we calculated the decrease in signal intensity by calculating the ratios of definite integrals between the injected substance and NaF. This relative ratio enables us to accurately assess the signal intensity and, thus, track the elimination of FluoroMic from the body (**Figure 2b**).

In total, we conducted nine measurements over 99 days, where all animals exhibited a similar trend, with signal intensity decreasing over time. Upon evaluation, we observed a clear two-phase decay curve ($R^2 = 0.99$) showcasing FluoroMic elimination from a body. This result indicates that the probe performs consistently within the biological system (**Figure S1**, Supporting Information). An initial, quick phase ($t_{1/2} \approx 18 \text{ h}$) was followed by a slower phase ($t_{1/2} \approx 18 \text{ days}$), as shown by a decrease in ^{19}F signal intensity. During our analysis, we also estimated the noise level in the MR spectroscopic data, which expresses the inherent background signal. This background signal can adversely impact

the clarity of the signal. In our study, the estimated noise level was $\approx 15\%$ of the signal intensity (**Figure 3**).

In vivo clearance is a complex process affected by various factors, such as size,^[32] structural coatings,^[33] and particle shape,^[34] collectively determining how long a carrier remains in circulation. For instance, a study by Staal et al.^[35] highlighted that their multi-core nanoparticles exhibited biological half-lives up to 15 times shorter than their single-core nanoemulsion counterparts. This observation underscores a clear relationship between nanoparticle ultrastructure and biological half-life. As a result, it becomes essential to evaluate the biological half-lives of substances administered in vivo and, when necessary, make adjustments to the polymer morphology to optimize clinical applications. As the size of FluoroMic unimers (individual polymer chains) is around 60 kDa (corresponding to $\approx 10 \text{ nm}$), which is very close to the renal filtration threshold,^[36] we expect that the main part of the polymer is excreted via kidneys.

2.3. Comparison between FluoroMic and FluoroMic+CFZ MR Properties

One of the main advantages of self-assembled micellar ^{19}F MRI tracers is their ability to encapsulate hydrophobic drugs. Encapsulation improves the water-solubility and pharmacokinetic profile of hydrophobic drugs, thus simultaneously supporting diagnosis and drug delivery. In this study, we loaded our micellar nanotracer FluoroMic with a model compound – the hydrophobic antimicrobial drug clofazimine, a known therapeutic agent for leprosy. This drug was loaded by direct encapsulation of the solid dispersion, resulting in a nanoformulation with 0.13 wt %

Figure 1. In vivo ^{19}F 2D MRSI hotspot: a) ^{19}F MRSI overlay with suppressed, low-intensity areas over a ^1H reference image at 30 min PI; b) ^{19}F MRSI overlay with suppressed low-intensity areas over a ^1H reference image at 5 days PI.

Figure 2. ^{19}F MRS of phantom and in vivo measurements: a) Two phantoms ($V = 500\ \mu\text{L}$) containing FluoroMic ($c = 60\ \text{mg mL}^{-1}$) and NaF ($c = 4.2\ \text{mg mL}^{-1}$) with their respective chemical shift $\Delta\delta \approx 47\ \text{ppm}$ (scan time = 1 min); b) in vivo ^{19}F MRS showing the decrease in FluoroMic content up to 99 days post-injection.

drug loading, henceforth referred to as FluoroMic+CFZ. By DLS analysis, we found that drug-loaded and drug-free micelles have an equivalent hydrodynamic diameter of $\approx 143\ \text{nm}$ (Figure 4a), thus showing that drug loading had a negligible effect on NP size. Given their similar polymer structure and size, the two formulations likely perform similarly within a biological system.

After drug encapsulation, we examined whether the two samples displayed matching MR parameters, such as relaxation times and sensitivity. For a proper assessment, the phantom samples containing FluoroMic and FluoroMic+CFZ were measured at the same volume

($V = 500\ \mu\text{L}$) and concentration ($c_{\text{pol}} = 60\ \text{mg mL}^{-1}$), with fluorine concentration (c_{F}) of $878\ \text{mmol L}^{-1}$ in the solution. On the NPs, ^{19}F MR relaxations were studied at two (1.5 and 4.7 T) magnetic field strengths. X-nuclei tracers should exhibit relatively short longitudinal T_1 relaxation times and long T_2 transverse relaxation times. Longer T_1 relaxation times prolong the

time required for the magnetization vector to reach equilibrium after each excitation, resulting in longer acquisition times. Conversely, longer T_2 relaxation times ensure a longer spin dephasing process, significantly slowing signal decay and ultimately increasing signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for both MRI and MRS.

The relaxation time measurements, conducted at 1.5 T and different temperatures, showed no significant differences, indicating the stability of the fluoropolymer probe under standard (20 °C) and physiological (37 °C) conditions. These findings were consistent with the measurements on the 4.7 T spectrometer, as shown in Table 1. The values highlight the favorable MR characteristics of the fluoropolymer probe, which has relatively short T_1 relaxation times and long T_2 relaxation times beneficial for precise and efficient MR applications.

Given their nearly identical relaxation rates and fluorine atom content ($c_{\text{F}} = 878\ \text{mmol L}^{-1}$), the samples were expected to perform consistently in ^{19}F MRS and MRI. Because the samples had an identical chemical shift, our ^{19}F MRS experiments required individual measurements. Nevertheless, this shared chemical shift enabled us to simultaneously measure the samples during ^{19}F MRSI experiments, providing more robust results.

When comparing ^{19}F NMR properties of drug-loaded and non-loaded NPs, the SNR at $c_{\text{pol}} = 30\ \text{mg mL}^{-1}$ was 136 for the fluorinated nanotracer and 104 for the micelle with encapsulated drug (Figure S2a, Supporting Information). As for the ^{19}F MRS experiment at 4.7 T, strong signals were obtained only after 1 s of measurement for both samples (Figure S2b, Supporting Information). After 30 s of measurement, the SNRs were 29.87 and 31.35 for FluoroMic and FluoroMic+CFZ, respectively (Figure 4b,d). The ^{19}F MRSI sequence also showed high probe sensitivity, with a clear signal after 1 min of measurement. Upon extending the measurement time to 10 min, we calculated SNRs of 19.8 and 20.9 for the non-loaded and drug-loaded polymers, respectively (Figure 4c,e).

Based on the equal NP sizes and outcomes of our MR comparison experiment, no significant difference in MR properties and sensitivity was found between FluoroMic and FluoroMic+CFZ.

Figure 3. Biphasic curve showing the elimination of FluoroMic from the body over time. The gray line at $y = 0.15$ depicts the approximate noise level below which we cannot clearly differentiate the injected fluoropolymer from spectral noise. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD.

Figure 4. Comparison between non-loaded (blue) and drug-loaded (red) phantom NPs: a) NP size before and after direct encapsulation of clofazimine ($c_{\text{pol}} = 1 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ in water); b) Variation of ^{19}F MRS SNR signal intensity as a function of scan time; c) Variation of ^{19}F MRSI SNR signal intensity as a function of scan time; d) ^{19}F MRS spectra of FluoroMic and FluoroMic+CFZ measured using a 30-s single-pulse sequence; e) ^{19}F MRSI data showing clear signal enhancement with prolonged scan times; the last column shows the corresponding reference ^1H MRI.

Therefore, using either the regular fluoropolymer or the drug-encapsulated polymer should not significantly impact the clearance. Moreover, the single-spectral peak, optimal relaxation times, and reasonably high fluorine content provide high tracing sensitivity, meeting the initial requirement for theranostics, that is, the ability to detect the administered substance within a biological system in a reasonable scan time and appropriate time window for effective monitoring.

Rapid advances in MRI instrumentation including cryogenically cooled radiofrequency coils and modified sequences such as ultrashort echo-time, hold the promise of significantly enhancing the sensitivity of our tracers. Especially for in vivo studies increased tracer sensitivity may decrease the volume of administration and shorten the acquisition time, thereby minimizing anesthesia duration and reducing animal discomfort during the imaging procedure.

2.4. Drug Encapsulation and Release

In vitro drug release was measured using the dialysis method in PBS (pH 7.4) at 37°C , mimicking the conditions in body fluids. The drug release profile followed a two-phase exponential association function ($R^2 = 0.99$), as found in other commonly used micellar drug-delivery systems, such as the anti-cancer drug doxorubicin.^[37–40] Our results showed a rapid release of $\approx 20\%$ of the loaded drug by non-specific clofazimine leaching from the outer part of the micelle core (burst release), followed by a much slower and sustained release of the remaining drug from the inner parts of the micelle core. Approximately 50% of the drug was released within 110 h of incubation (Figure 5), in line with our diagnostic capability of visualizing the substance even at 5 days PI. The drug release process depends not only on the polymer structure but also on external conditions,^[41] highlighting the

Table 1. MR relaxometry properties of FluoroMic and FluoroMic+CFZ nanoparticles measured under different conditions.

Sample	1.5 T at 20°C		1.5 T at 37°C		4.7 T at 20°C	
	T_1 [ms]	T_2 [ms]	T_1 [ms]	T_2 [ms]	T_1 [ms]	T_2 [ms]
FluoroMic	386	73	367	69	393	77
FluoroMic+CFZ	380	70	383	73	387	79

Figure 5. In vitro clofazimine release from the nanotracer incubated in PBS (pH 7.4) at 37 °C, fitted to a two-phase exponential association curve.

importance of mimicking the internal environment of an organism (37 °C and pH 7.4). However, the variation in pH and temperature dependence provides a prospective option for stimuli-responsive or on-off polymers.^[42,43] Ultimately, the drug release kinetics and biological half-life of these nanoparticles establish a basis for further optimizing drug delivery strategies and determining critical time points for in vivo imaging.

assessment was performed using a standard H&E staining protocol to examine the subcutaneous and muscle tissues surrounding the injection site, using the contralateral tissues used as controls (Figure 6) to confirm NP biocompatibility. Tissues for histological examination were extracted five months after 200 μ L of FluoroMic injection. Upon histomorphological analysis, the skeletal muscle and adipose tissue revealed completely normal characteristics, including intact peripheral nerves and blood vessels. Considering the absence of adverse effects and significant changes in the biological tissues, with no signs of cellular damage, inflammatory responses, or tissue degeneration, these data provide compelling evidence of the non-toxicity and high biocompatibility of FluoroMic.

3. Conclusion

Fluorine-loaded amphiphilic, self-assembled, micellar nanoparticles can encapsulate hydrophobic drugs, in our case the non-steroidal antileptotic drug clofazimine, and serve as high-sensitivity imaging tracers for ¹⁹F MRI. Based on the drug release profile, these nanoparticles rapidly release the drug in an initial phase, which is followed by a much slower and sustained release, and 50% of the drug is released within 110 h from incubation. After their subcutaneous injection, ¹⁹F MR hotspot images of the injection site can be acquired even after 5 days, demonstrating the ongoing clearance process, as shown by in vivo ¹⁹F MRS. Additionally, histological assessment of these nanoparticles confirmed their non-toxicity and high biocompatibility at relatively low magnetic field strength (4.7 T), underscoring the relevance of the results for potential clinical applications. Overall, this study presents the design of a biocompatible theranostics platform, which can be tailored to meet specific needs in various

settings thanks to the versatility of polymer chain modification. Moreover, this innovative development opens up multiple opportunities for theranostics, combining therapeutic and diagnostic components.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: If not stated otherwise, all chemicals, including clofazimine, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. 2,2'-Azobis[2-(2-imidazolyl)propane]dichloride (VA-044) initiator was purchased from TCI Europe. N-(2-Hydroxyethyl)acrylamide (HEAM) was filtered through a short pad of basic alumina before use to remove the inhibitor. The PEG-CTA and N-(2,2,2-trifluoromethyl)acrylamide (TFEAM) were synthesized according to literature protocols.^[29,44] Water was deionized with a Millipore Milli-Q water purification system.

Synthesis of Fluorinated Nanoparticles by Aqueous Dispersion PISA of TFEAM: Fluorinated block copolymer NPs were synthesized by RAFT-mediated dispersion PISA of TFEAM in water. In the synthesis of PEG₉₁-b-P(TFEAM-*stat*-HEAM)₄₀₀ (total solids content 6 wt.%), TFEAM (449 mg, 2.93 mmol), PEG-BTPA (38.5 mg, 0.0091 mmol), HEAM (84.35 mg, 0.773 mmol), VA-044 (0.74 mg, 0.0022 mmol, [CTA]₀/[VA-044]₀ = 4:1), and the internal standard 1,3,5-trioxane (5 mg) were dissolved in distilled water (9.3 mL), purged with nitrogen gas and stirred in an aluminum heating block at 50 °C for 5 h. The reaction was quenched by exposure to air followed by ¹H and ¹⁹F nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) analysis. Monomer conversion was determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy of the reaction mixture upon dilution with CD₃OD by comparing the residual vinyl peaks at 5.5–6.5 ppm with the signal of the internal standard.

Drug Loading Into Nanoparticles: Before the drug encapsulation, the NPs were freeze-dried, and dissolved in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (12 mL, pH 7.4, $c_{\text{pol}} = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) along with a non-steroidal drug clofazimine ($m = 5 \text{ mg}$). The solution was stirred at room temperature, in the dark, for 3 weeks, and then centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 2 min to remove the non-encapsulated drug. Drug-loaded NPs were characterized by dynamic light scattering (DLS). The amount of loaded clofazimine was determined by UV-vis spectrometry. The nanoformulation (100 μ L) was diluted with 900 μ L of methanol, and the clofazimine content was determined by UV-vis spectrometry at 459 nm using clofazimine calibration. Drug loading was calculated as $DL = \frac{m_{\text{clof}}}{(m_{\text{pol}} + m_{\text{clof}})} \times 100\%$, where m_{clof} and m_{pol} represent the weight amounts of the solubilized clofazimine and copolymer in the dispersion, respectively.

Characterization of Copolymer Nanoparticles and Drug Formulations: Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements were used to determine the hydrodynamic diameters of the polymers in distilled water on a ZEN3600 Zetasizer Nano-ZS zeta potential analyzer (Malvern Instruments, UK). The polymer samples ($c_{\text{pol}} = 1 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$). The apparent Z-averaged hydrodynamic diameter of the particles, D_h , was determined at a scattering angle of $\theta = 173^\circ$, using Zetasizer software to evaluate the data. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Advance MSL 400 MHz NMR spectrometer at 25 °C in a mixture of H₂O/D₂O (95/5 v/v). Unless stated otherwise, all ¹⁹F NMR spectra were measured at $c_{\text{pol}} = 30 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$, 20 μ s pulse width, 8-s relaxation delay, and 1.5-s acquisition time in 64 scans, expressing all chemical shifts as ppm. The NMR spectra were processed using MestReNova 14.1 software, and the signal-to-noise ratios were calculated using the built-in MestReNova function.

Magnetic Resonance Relaxometry: To evaluate the ¹⁹F relaxation times of NPs, a 1.5 T Minispec 60 MHz relaxometer (Bruker Biospin, Germany) equipped with a probe adjusted to a proper resonance frequency of 54 MHz for ¹⁹F was used. Before placing the samples in the relaxometer, the phantoms were thermostatted at 20 and 37 °C (Biosan CH 3–150, Latvia). The T_1 relaxation times were measured with the following inversion recovery sequence: repetition time (TR) = 0.01–5000 ms; recycle delay = 1 s; scans = 4; 10 points per fitting. A Carr–Purcell–Meiboom–Gill (CPMG) sequence was used to assess T_2 relaxation times with the following parameters: Echo time (TE) = 0.04 ms; TR = 5000 ms; recycle delay = 2 s; number of scans = 8; 20 000 points per fitting.

Figure 6. H&E stain histomorphological examination showing normal histomorphology in the injection site (left) and contralateral, control (right) tissues with the scale on the bottom right corner.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging and Spectroscopy: The Bruker Biospec 47/20 4.7T MR experimental scanner (Bruker Biospec, Ettlingen, Germany) was utilized to perform a series of aqueous phantom and in vivo MR experiments, using a custom-made double tunable $^1\text{H}/^{19}\text{F}$ surface single-loop radiofrequency (RF) coil with a 4-cm diameter. The RF coil has the ability to tune and match the Larmor frequencies of both ^1H and ^{19}F nuclei for optimal performance.^[45] Reference hydrogen ^1H MR images were acquired using a T_2 -weighted fast spin-echo sequence with the following parameters: TR = 3300 ms; TE = 11.70 ms; effective echo time, TE_{eff} = 35.10 ms; turbo factor = 8; spatial resolution = $0.156 \times 0.156 \text{ mm}^2$; Scan time = 1 min 19 s. To further characterize the MR properties of the NPs, ^{19}F relaxation times were also evaluated using a regular single-pulse sequence (TR = 75–2500 ms) for T_1 and CPMG (TE = 1–200 ms; TR = 500) for T_2 . Probe sensitivity was assessed using a single-pulse sequence (TR = 500 ms; number of averages = 2–600). ^{19}F MR images were acquired by MRSI, a spectrally resolved method, from a 2D slab of voxels with the following parameters: TR = 200 ms; TE = 15 ms; bandwidth, BW = 38 ppm; spatial resolution = $2.5 \times 2.5 \times 16 \text{ mm}^3$, Scan time = 1–10 min. In vivo measurements were also taken using the MRSI method with a scan time of 15 min. By opting for the ^{19}F MRSI method over conventional ^{19}F MRI (e.g., spin-echo sequence), the authors were able to precisely separate and visualize the targeted signal at a specific resonance frequency. This choice was made to overcome any potential interference between the signals emitted by the injected polymer and the anesthetic isoflurane gas. A non-localized ^{19}F MRS single-pulse sequence (TR = 200 ms, BW = 200 ppm, scan time = 15 min) was used to assess the clearance of the administered NPs.

In Vivo Setup and Handling: An in vivo clearance analysis was conducted with healthy female BALB/c mice ($n = 3$), which were subcutaneously injected with a PBS solution of the fluorinated polymer ($c_{\text{pol}} = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) into their right hind leg ($V = 100 \mu\text{L}$). The molar concentration of fluorine (c_{F}) in the solution is 878 mmol L^{-1} . Individual measurements ($m = 9$) were taken for 99 days PI, with the first measurement taken ≈ 30 -min PI. General anesthesia was induced with 5% isoflurane gas (Baxter, Deerfield, USA), at a flow rate of 1.5–0.5%, maintained during the measurement. Throughout the scanning, the breathing rate was monitored using a pressure sensor (Rapid Biomedical, Berlin, Germany) inserted beneath the abdomen. To prevent corneal damage, eye ointment (Ophtalmo-Septonex, Zentiva, Czech Republic) was applied to the eyes. The animal was placed in the MR scanner with two Eppendorf tubes containing fluorinated solutions arranged under its hind legs for reference purposes. One Eppendorf tube, containing the PBS solution of the polymer ($V = 100 \mu\text{L}$) injected into the murine leg, was positioned contralaterally to the injection site, to serve as a control for ^{19}F MRSI data, and subsequently removed before the ^{19}F MRS measurement. The other Eppendorf tube, containing an aqueous solution of NaF with a volume of $100 \mu\text{L}$ and concentration of 4.2 mg mL^{-1} , was placed under the right leg of the animal for quantitative purposes (Figure S3, Supporting Information). All animal protocols were approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine and by the Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic (no.58/2014) in accordance with the Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes.

Magnetic Resonance Data Processing and Quantitation: i) ^{19}F MR non-localized spectroscopy and ii) MRSI data were mostly quantified and processed in the programming environment MATLAB (<https://mathworks.com>, Matlab R2022a, The MathWorks, Inc., USA) using custom-written scripts. i) In vivo clearance was assessed by calculating the relative ratio between the phased integral peaks of the injected polymer and the reference NaF phantom. Zero-filling with a factor of 2 was used to improve spectral resolution. No other post-processing techniques (e.g., apodization) were applied during quantitation to avoid spectral distortion. All values are expressed as mean \pm SD. ii) The final in vivo ^{19}F MRSI and phantom images were reconstructed as a normalized maximum intensity projection of selected slices along the frequency axis while applying a specific color map. Bilinear interpolation was used to convert ^{19}F MR images from a 64×64 to a 256×256 matrix to match the size to the reference image. The SNR ratio of phantom MRSI images was calculated by dividing the mean signal of the region of interest by the average standard deviation of noise. Given the Rician noise distribution, the result was multiplied with a correction factor of 0.655. The spectroscopic SNR was quantified by dividing the signal height by the noise standard deviation.

Release Studies of Clofazimine-Loaded Polymer Nanoparticle: Drug release was analyzed using the dialysis method. For this purpose, the clofazimine-loaded polymer nanotracer (0.5 mL, $c = 10 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) was transferred to Pur-A-Lyzer Midi dialysis Kits. The dialysis kits were then placed in a beaker filled with PBS buffer media thermostat at 37°C . At different time points (0, 1, 3, 4.5, 14, 24, and 112 h), 0.1 mL was removed from each sample and added to 0.9 mL of methanol, and the clofazimine concentration was measured on a UV-vis spectrophotometer ($\lambda = 459 \text{ nm}$) in triplicates. All values were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

Histological Examination: To verify the non-toxicity and biocompatibility of the NPs, the authors euthanized a mouse injected with the studied fluoropolymer ($V = 200 \mu\text{L}$, $c_{\text{pol}} = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) 5 months PI and conducted standard a histological protocol with hematoxylin-eosin (H&E) staining to detect any potential pathologies.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

clofazimine, fluorine-19, magnetic resonance, nanoparticles, polymerization-induced self-assembly, theranostics

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